

ISic0101

I.Sicily inscription 0101

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. Q(uintus) · Decumius · Q(uinti) · f(ilius)

2. II · vir

3. porticus · de · s[uo]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Quintus Decumius son of Quintus, duovir, (erected this) porticus at his own expense.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285308
EDR 127536
EDCS 22100054

Bibliography

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